

**ETHNIC DESCRIPTION OF THE “TAGCHI” CLAN OF THE
SURKHAN OASIS AS AN EXAMPLE OF ETHNOGRAPHER B.H.
KARMISHEVA’S RESEARCH**

Turaev Sherzod

PhD student of Termiz State University

After our country gained national independence historical truth free from ideological pressure and influences in an objective, factual, justice and historical perspective we had the opportunity to convey to our people. The history of the emergence of ethnic groups in the Surkhan oasis is ethnic formation is a long and complex process. Historical development ethnic units were formed in the oasis and they are unique created a way of life, economic activities and customs. In the monograph of the linguist Kh. Doniyorov in the Southern Surkhan oasis to the history of the Uzbek peoples, such as the living kungirat, katagan and tagchi there is information about [1, B.83]. Tagchies, toqchi, toxchi - one of the ancient indigenous (autochthonous) Turkic peoples of south Uzbekistan. The word Tagchi means “mountainous”. The ancestors of the tagchies in the territory of South Uzbekistan lived even before the arrival of the Uzbeks [2, B.112]

As a result of B.K. Karmisheva's research in the Surkhan oasis There are created monographs and articles about the unique ethnic and social status of the oasis. The scientist covered the entire region of Central Asia Ethnogenesis of every clan, tribe and nation and collected data on ethnic history, material and spiritual a researcher who conducted in-depth scientific research on culture [3, B.22] The author gives a list of 32 Uzbek clans and their expresses his opinion about the features of the location. In particular, there is a lot of information about tagchi peoples in his works caused. [4, B.46]

This people is called tagchies because they live in the mountains. In terms of numbers, Tagchies mainly live in the Surkhandarya oasis they got up after the kungirats

and chigatays. At the beginning of the last century the population of the oasis is mainly was located on the Surkhandarya, Sherobodarya and its tributaries. Such regional locations of ethnic groups it hasn't changed much to this day. In the villages Qizilnavr, Kegdala, Orikli of the Sheroboddarya there is tagchi tribe of the katagans ethnic group

Representatives of this group often called themselves katagans. A large Uzbek tribe of Dashti Kipchaks is known under this name but the Tagchies did not consider themselves Uzbeks at all, As their name suggests, they are Tagchies often lived in high mountains. In a 1924 survey the Tagchies are not mentioned separately, but the repression of the Uzbeks given as belonging to the tribe. Therefore, the Tagchies are in this area It has a population of 5605 and is located on the eastern side of the Kohitang Mountains 1,190 in the banks, 2,695 in the middle stream basin of Sheroboddarya, 665 in the upper reaches of Sherobodarya, in the Surkhan basin 1055 people lived on the right bank. The Tagchies are in Sherjand on the eastern slopes of Kohitang mountains (together with Tajiks), Zarbog (Khoja together with Tajiks and Uzbeks), He lived in the villages of Khojank, Bedakata, Sher-kisloq and Zarautsoy. There were two large mountain villages, Khatak and Tangiduval, in the basin of the middle stream of Sheroboddarya. There were 500 houses in Khatak. Their language and in terms of lifestyle, it was close to the Chigatoys. This of the villages The inhabitants of the group were called Hataksam-Hataks. They considered themselves to belong to the Sariboshkhatagon clan and to the following groups divided into: Sher, Baymak, Khidir, Kuchak [5, B.83-85].

The Tagchies who lived in the upper reaches of the Sheroboddarya belonged to the Chubashkhatagon clan, Kyzylnur, Komurchi, Koksoi, He occupied Kentala villages. Between Chubash-repressions The names of two groups of Tagchies are mentioned - Khudoyberdi and Almakhat. Tajik-Chagatoys in Boisun city and Naulion, Sarysia lived together with Chigatoy, Khoja and Kungirats in the village, and Barlos in Regarda. In the Surkhan basin, Tagchies lived in the villages of Qairok, Gashnaz, Qizilqishloq, Saroytash, Bagchiq and Khojaparnavat. The Tagchin villages of Changlak, Chakana and Bakhcha are located in the Sangardak gorge. Among them,

Changlak, the largest village, had 400 households at the beginning of the 20th century, according to the testimony of the elderly. In the 19th century, these three villages were summer camps for Tagchies, and in winter, most of them went to the Surkhan valley - Yurchi, Denov and Sariasia districts. The Tagchies are located in the villages of Takhchi, Tutay and Tagitova on the left bank of To palang. To the east of the city of Denov, the Tagchies were recorded only at one point together with the barlos belonging to the Jatta clan. It should be noted that the toponym Tagchies is pronounced as Tokhchi by the local population. In general, Tagchies are divided into joints such as korapoycha, ajina, norkal, botashshig, hoyaki, komurchi. They are mainly engaged in animal husbandry, horticulture and partly farming. [5, B.83]

As noted by B. Kh. Karmisheva, Boysun Tagchies were part of the chagatai. Tagchies made up 20.3% of the population in Boysun. Takchida believed that their ancestors came from Kunduz, Tashkurgan and Balkh. In the Poshkhurd valley, there is information that the Tagchies have connections with their relatives who stayed on the left bank of the Amudarya. The information about the period when the ancestors of the Tagchies came here varies greatly from 200 to 800 years. At the end of the 60s of the XIX century A.D. Grebenkin Samarkand region among the repressors, there is a legend that their ancestors emigrated from Kunduz during the reign of Abdulaziz Khan.

Some of the Tagchies lived in houses typical of semi- nomadic Uzbeks from the steppe Kipchaks, but they considered the karluq- type hut to be the original form of their place of residence. Tagchies absorbed the anthropological image of the Iranian-speaking local population, adopted the features of the culture of the aboriginal settled population. According to B. L. Grombchevskiy, the clothes of tagchies at that time did not differ from the clothes of Tadjiks.

“Surkhan is the ancient cradle of the world civilization to world the land of the Bactrian and Kushan states is popular” [6, B.376]. Death of thieves in the Surkhan oasis is incomparable. According to scientist B.Kh. Karmisheva, the clan of tagchi is ancient in the oasis included in the population category. From their anthropological characteristics comes out and claims that Mongoloid is more racial. In addition, most

of the Tagchies live in the Surkhan collective farm of Zharkorgan district, Khazarbagh collective farm of Denov district and Muzrobod districts. Due to the economic and political processes that took place at the beginning of the XX century, most of the tagchi were absorbed into the Uzbeks, and some groups were absorbed into the Tajiks. This ethnic group created its own customs, ethnoculture, rituals. In a word, this ethnic group created the ethnography of the Surkhan oasis.

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